

Welcome to the fifth edition of the ENTRUST newsletter! The past six months were full of activities, meetings and work for the ENTRUST project. Discover more about these topics and get the latest updates about the project in this edition of our newsletter.

Tackling the lack of cybersecurity implementations in CMDs

As the ENTRUST project progresses, we wanted to remind you of its use cases. The project's framework will be evaluated in four real-world use cases ranging from wearable and medical devices used for remote patient monitoring to high-end stationary equipment used in hospitals and clinics.

[Learn more](#)

Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting

Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data

Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Well-being of Patients and Carers

Ambient Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living

ENTRUST Midterm Review Meeting and 4th Plenary Meeting in Paris

On the end of September 2024, the EnTrust Project consortium successfully presented the progress during the Midterm Review meeting, while on December 3rd-4th gathered for the **4th Plenary Meeting** in Paris, France.

[Learn more](#)

Latest from our blog

ENTRUST IoT Security Architecture Presented at Saudi Aramco Cybersecurity Chair

[Learn more](#)

Expert Interviews: Cybersecurity Innovations for Connected Medical Devices: Interview with UBITECH

[Learn more](#)

Surveys

Ethical and Legal Considerations in Connected Medical Devices – Insights from Technology Users

Perspectives on Transparency, Security, and Trust in Connected Medical Devices

Partners

